

Preparation and Study of Ionisation Quotients of Some Hydroxylamine Derivatives and the Effect of Substituents on pK_a Values

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N-Benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine and some of its analogues have been prepared by improved method and their ionisation quotients in 70% dioxan-water mixture have been determined potentiometrically. The titration medium was maintained at a constant ionic strength (0.1 M KCl) and at a temperature, $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The effect of substituents on pK_a values has been discussed.

N-Benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine (BPHA), introduced by Shome¹, is one of the most interesting of the many organic reagents which have been suggested in recent years. Looking to its analytical usefulness, the work on the determination of stabilities of metal chelates of BPHA and its analogues was undertaken in our laboratories^{2,3}. In this connection some of these compounds were prepared and the method given by Shome¹ has been improved to make it simpler. The present communication also deals with the determination of ionisation quotients of these compounds in 70% v/v dioxan-water mixture and the effect of different substituents on pK_a values.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of BPHA : The method consists in reacting phenyl-hydroxylamine with molar proportion of benzoyl chloride in slightly alkaline medium at 0° . The mono and derivatives formed are separated by treating the mixture with ammonia liquor, which dissolves the former. In the method given by Shome freshly prepared crystalline phenyl-hydroxylamine is used. We have, however, directly benzoylated phenylhydroxylamine solution, as it was obtained by reducing nitrobenzene with zinc dust in ammonium chloride solution. Further, the reaction with benzoyl chloride was carried out at room temperature (using water trough, temperature $20-25^\circ$) and not at 0° . The course of the reaction was followed by testing a drop of reaction mixture with Tollen's reagent. Negative test indicated the completion of the reaction.

Other BPHA analogues were similarly prepared. N-Anisoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine was prepared by reducing nitrobenzene (12.3 g., 0.1 mole) and then reacting it with anisoyl chloride (19.5 g., 0.1 mole). It was crystallised from alcohol as white needles. Yield : 12.8 g., m.p. 130° . Analysis Found : C, 69.00; H, 5.21; N, 5.59%; $C_{14}H_{13}NO_3$ requires : C, 69.11; H, 5.39; N, 5.76%.

1. S. C. Shome, *Analyst*, 1950, **75**, 27.
2. J. P. C. Jaimini, *Ph.D. Thesis*, University of Rajasthan, 1966.
3. J. P. C. Jaimini and N. C. Sogani, *Z. Naturforschung*, 1967, **22**, 922; *Z. anorg. allg. Chemie*, 1967, **355**, 332; *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 59; *Jour. Inst. of Chem.*, 1968, **40**, 52.

N-Acetyl-N-*p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine was prepared from 15.7 g. *p*-chloronitrobenzene (0.1 mole) and 7.8 g. acetylchloride (0.1 mole). It was crystallised from benzene petroleum-ether mixture as white needles. Yield: 10.4 g., m.p. 114°. Analysis Found: C, 51.58; H, 4.29; N, 7.51; Cl, 19.00%. $C_8H_8NO_2Cl$ requires: C, 51.70; H, 4.34; N, 7.54; Cl, 19.08%.

N-Acetyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine was prepared by following the method given by Gupta and Sogani⁴ and N-benzoylhydroxylamine by Blatt⁵.

Determination of Ionisation Quotients: Ionisation quotients of these compounds were determined by following the method given by Albert and Sergeant⁶. pH measurements were made with a Cambridge Bench-Type pH Meter, calibrated to 0.02 unit. Sodium hydroxide solution was standardised with A.R. grade potassium hydrogen phthalate. B.D.H. dioxan was purified by Weissberger's method⁷.

Potentiometric Titration: Ten millilitres of 0.05 *M* compound solution in 70% v/v dioxan-water mixture was taken in a 100-ml. beaker. 2.5 ml. of 2 *M* KCl was added to maintain the constant ionic strength of 0.1 *M*. The total volume of the contents was made to 47.5 ml. by adding varying amounts of dioxan and distilled water in such proportions that it finally became 70% v/v dioxan-water mixture. The temperature of the solution was maintained at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$. 0.1 *N* NaOH solution was added to it in ten equal portions, each a tenth of an equivalent, and pH was recorded as soon as equilibrium was reached. Titrations, carried out in duplicate, were reproducible within ± 0.02 pH unit.

TABLE I

Ionisation Quotient of N-Benzoyl-N-phenyl-hydroxylamine

Compound concentration = 0.01 *M* at half neutralisation
 Ionic strength = 0.1 *M* KCl
 Temperature = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$
 Medium = 70% v/v dioxan-water.

Titrant 0.1 <i>N</i> NaOH ml.	pH	Stoichiometric concentrations		OH ⁻ .10 ⁻⁴	log $\frac{HA + OH^-}{A^- - OH^-}$	pK _a
		HA.10 ⁻³	A.10 ⁻³			
0.50	9.95	9	1	0.9	+1.00	10.95
1.00	10.29	8	2	2.0	+0.66	10.95
1.50	10.52	7	3	3.0	+0.43	10.95
2.00	10.70	6	4	5.0	+0.27	10.97
2.50	10.84	5	5	7.0	+0.12	10.96
3.00	10.97	4	6	9.0	-0.02	10.95
3.50	11.10	3	7	13.0	-0.12	10.98
4.00	11.20	2	8	16.0	-0.25	10.96
4.50	11.32	1	9	21.0	-0.34	10.98

$pK_a = 10.96 \pm 0.02$ (using all nine values of the set).

- H. K. L. Gupta and N. C. Sogani, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 769.
- A. H. Blatt, "*Organic Synthesis*," Collective vol. 2, John Wiley, 1950, p. 67; Vol. 1, 1951, p. 318.
- A. Albert and E. P. Serjeant, "Ionisation Constants of Acids and Bases", John Wiley, 1962, p. 171.
- A. Weissberger and E. S. Proskaver, "Organic Solvents", Oxford, 1935, p. 139.

The results of titration of BPHA are recorded in Table I. For the sake of brevity, results of titrations of remaining compounds are not given here. The pK_a values of these compounds are compiled in Table II.

TABLE II

Ionisation Quotients of hydroxylamine derivatives

Ionic strength	= 0.1 M KCl
Temperature	= $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$
Medium	= 70% v/v dioxan-water

No.	Compound		$pK_a \pm .02$
	R	R'	
I	C_6H_5	C_6H_5	10.96
II	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_3(p)$	C_6H_5	11.08
III	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_3(o)$	C_6H_5	11.01
IV	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{Cl}(p)$	C_6H_5	10.78
V	C_6H_5	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{OCH}_3(p)$	11.18
VI	C_6H_5	CH_3	11.40
VII	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{Cl}(p)$	CH_3	10.91
VIII	H	C_6H_5	10.35

DISCUSSION

Effect of substitution on pK_a values: The dissociation of substituted compounds will depend upon the nature and position of groups present in the rings

A comparison of the pK_a values (Table II) reveals that compound II, having a methyl group at position 4 in ring A, is slightly higher than the parent compound I. This is due to +I effect of the methyl group. Such a group at position 2 in ring A (comp. III) should increase the pK_a value to a greater extent than at position 4 due to the nearness of +I effect on -OH bearing nitrogen atom. However, contrary is the case. The lower pK_a value of the *ortho*- than the *para*- isomer is due to the *ortho*- effect of the methyl group resulting in decrease in electron density on the nitrogen atom.

Substitution of a methoxy group at position 4 in ring B (comp. V) increases pK_a value over the parent compound I, presumably due to the -M effect of the substituent.

Compound IV, having a *chloro* group at position 4 in ring A, has a lower *pKa* value than the parent compound. This indicates that +M effect of chlorine is not operative in this compound otherwise the *pKa* value should have increased. Thus, -I effect of chlorine atom appears to be affecting the ionisation of the compound. Similarly, chlorine at position 4 in *N*-acetyl-*N*-phenyl-hydroxylamine (comp. VII) decreases the *pKa* value of the substituted compound.

Compound I has a lower *pKa* value than *N*-acetyl-*N*-phenyl-hydroxylamine (comp. VI). This is due to the change from -I effect of the aryl group to +I effect of the methyl group in the latter compound.

Comparison of pKa values of N-benzoyl N-phenylhydroxylamine (I) and N-benzoylhydroxylamine (VIII): The *pKa* value of the former compound (10.96) in 70% v/v dioxan-water mixture is higher than the latter (10.35). This is contrary to our expectations. Replacement of an electron withdrawing phenyl group with a hydrogen atom in compound VIII should have increased the *pKa* value instead of decreasing it. However, this is not the case in aqueous medium and the order of their *pKa* values is as expected (*pKa*, I = 8.22 and VIII = 8.76). Hence, it was considered worthwhile to determine *pKa* values of these compounds in different dioxan-water mixtures. The method adopted was the same as described above. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

pKa values of *N*-Benzoyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine (I) and
N-Benzoylhydroxylamine (VIII)

Dioxan-water % dioxan	<i>pKa</i> I	<i>pKa</i> VIII
0	8.22 (8.15)*	8.76 (8.89)†
10	8.58	8.98
20	9.00	9.20
30	9.42	9.44
40	9.96	9.68
50	10.22	9.92
60	10.64	10.14
70	10.96	10.35

* D. Dryssen, *Acta. Chem. Scand*, 1956, **10**, 353.

† Wise and Brandt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1058.

The *pKa* values, as expected, increase with the increase in the proportion of dioxan in the medium, but this increase in the case of the former compound (I) is more than the latter (VIII). In 30% dioxan-water medium, the *pKa* values of both the compounds are approximately the same. This unusual effect of dioxan concentration on the *pKa* values is not easily explainable.

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